

AMIGDALA

Alliance for Modelling Industries towards the
Green Deal's objectives and circuLArity

D5.3 – Dissemination & Communication Plan No. 2

Lead Beneficiary: SIE

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1. AMIGDALA Project Summary

Transitioning industries towards climate neutrality by 2050, as directed by the European Green Deal, presents a multi-faceted challenge. Sustainable industry for Europe must become climate-neutral, while also remaining globally competitive and resilient. Changing course requires foresight to oversee the complex interplay between demand, global trade and industrial production. Decision-makers will choose from options available to them, to make policy, regulate or invest in the deployment of novel technologies in public infrastructure and industrial assets.

The objective of the EU-funded AMIGDALA project is to deliver policy scenarios and projections of industrial development based on indicators and control options that decision-makers recognize.

For the projections, an integrated modelling tool will be developed that links demand & trade, industrial production, primary generation of energy & feedstock and climate effects, spanning the period 1990 to 2070. Modelling of local decision-making will zoom into the options and choices made by industry clusters and the utility operators that provide them with resources.

2. Executive summary

This document presents the second version of the AMIGDALA project's Dissemination and Communication (D&C) Plan. It provides an overview of the strategy, with a particular focus on monitoring key performance indicators (KPIs) established to track partner activities and evaluate the impact of communication efforts to date.

Building on the foundation set by the initial plan ([D5.2](#)), this update focuses on evaluating the effectiveness of the communication activities implemented during the first 18 months of the project. It provides an analysis of the key performance indicators (KPIs) established to monitor progress, assess the impact of communication efforts, and ensure the strategy remains aligned with project objectives.

The plan continues to outline the project's target audiences, key messages, communication channels, and roles and responsibilities. It also includes updates to the project's branding elements, such as the logo, templates, social media profiles, and website, ensuring consistency and engagement across all communication platforms. As a dynamic document, the D&C plan will remain under continuous review and refinement throughout the project to ensure communications are effective, relevant, and responsive to evolving needs. To help readers navigate the structure of the document, it's useful to highlight that it is organized in two main parts:

1. **Strategy and Setup** – Chapters 1–11 outline what was defined in the Grant Agreement: the strategic framework, tools, and plans.
2. **Actions and Analysis** – Chapter 12 presents what was actually done during M6–M18, including performance against KPIs and interpretation of results.

The D&C strategy is structured in four key stages:

- **Initial Plan ([D5.2](#)):** Delivered in month 6, this version established the foundational communication strategy, including identification of target audiences, key messaging, channels, and partner roles. The project branding elements were finalized by month 3.
- **Second Update ([D5.3](#)) – This Document:** this version focuses on assessing the effectiveness of communication activities during the first year and a half of the project. It evaluates performance

against the KPIs and suggests adjustments where needed to optimize ongoing efforts.

- **Third Update (D6.1):** Scheduled for delivery in Month 36 (M36), this version will focus on the communication aspects of collaboration activities and stakeholder engagement in the later phases of the project.
- **Final Update (D7.1):** To be delivered in Month 48 (M48), this version will provide a comprehensive review of all dissemination and communication activities carried out throughout the project, offering insights into the overall impact and lessons learned.

2.1 Context of WP5-7: Dissemination, exploitation and communication (DEC) – Reporting Period 1/2/3

The main goal of the work package 5 (WP5), Dissemination, exploitation and communication (DEC) – Reporting Period 1, is to coordinate the efforts of the consortium between month 1 and month 18 to actively involve the project's stakeholders in the open R&D cycle of the project, from the design phase to the outputs' review, validation and uptake, and maximise the impact by adequately conveying the project's messages and results to targeted audiences and preparing IP and exploitation measures for the results. The following work package (WP6) covers the second period, from month 19 (M19) to month 36 (M36), of the project's Dissemination, Exploitation, and Communication activities, continuing the work of WP5. This subsequent work package (WP7) ensures the continuity and progression of DEC activities into the project's third period, building on the foundations laid by WP5.

2.2 Objectives of Tasks 5.2, 6.1, 7.1 – D&C Activities

The aim of this task is to prepare and execute the project's dissemination and communication plan. SIE will coordinate the work, preparing the different deliveries of the D&C plan ([D5.2](#) in M6, [D5.3](#) in M18, [D6.1](#) in M36 and [D7.1](#) in M48) and updating the different activities performed by partners.

This [first D&C plan](#) by M6 outlined the project’s audiences, key messages, and channels for the communication and the dissemination, including roles and responsibilities. The project branding (logo, templates, etc.), social media profiles and website were ready in M3 (Milestone 13). The task 6.1 will continue the work of T5.2, implementing the DEC activities during the 2nd reporting period of the project. The activities will be monitored and reviewed in the M36 update (D6.1).

Finally, the 7.1 task will continue the work of T6.1, implementing the dissemination and communication activities during the last reporting period of the project. The activities will be monitored and reviewed in the M48 update (D7.1).

3. Acronyms and abbreviations

COP	Community of Practice
D&C PLAN	Dissemination and Communication
D-FRAMEWORK	Decision-framework
DOA	Description of action
EC	European Commission
ECEMF	European Climate + Energy Modelling Forum
GA4	Google Analytics 4
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GP	General Public
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
OEM	Original Equipment Manufacturer
OPEN ENT	open ENergy TRansition ANalyses for a low-Carbon Economy
PM	Policy Makers
P4PLANET	Processes4Planet
R&D	Research and Development

SC	Scientific Community
SIE	Sustainable Innovations Europe
SI	Software industry
TM	Trade Media
WP	Work Package

4. Introduction

This document presents the second version of the AMIGDALA project's Dissemination and Communication Plan, offering an updated overview of the strategy guiding the project's outreach and engagement efforts. A central focus of this update is the evaluation of key performance indicators established to monitor partner activities and assess the impact of communication initiatives over the past 18 months. Building upon the foundation laid in the initial plan ([D5.2](#)), this version analyzes how communication activities have evolved, evaluates their effectiveness, and ensures continued alignment with the project's overarching objectives.

During this period, communication efforts have been carried out consistently. These include biannual newsletters, weekly social media posts, and monthly website updates. This regular pace has allowed the consortium to monitor progress, assess communication effectiveness, and adjust the strategy as needed.

The D&C Plan outlines a comprehensive approach to engaging diverse stakeholder groups. It defines tailored messaging for each audience, identifies the most suitable communication channels, and details the development of impactful content such as newsletters, social media updates, and project videos. The plan also highlights the importance of maintaining a strong visual identity, complying with EU funding visibility requirements, and raising the project's profile through strategic press releases and event participation.

A targeted social media strategy will continue to drive stakeholder engagement, while informative materials will keep audiences informed and involved. The plan also describes the methodology for distributing project information, ensuring it reaches the right audience at the right time.

This document also reflects on the communication activities undertaken during the past 18 months, providing important context for future planning. By addressing these components, the D&C Plan aims to support the effective and impactful dissemination of AMIGDALA project results throughout its lifecycle.

5. Objectives of the D&C Plan

The AMIGDALA project's D&C Plan focuses on maximizing the reach and impact of its research findings. The plan prioritizes targeted dissemination by identifying specific audiences who will benefit most. This includes researchers, industry stakeholders, and policymakers. By understanding their needs, the D&C Plan shapes communication strategies for each group, ensuring that clear and impactful messaging resonates with them.

The plan acknowledges the importance of selecting the right communication channels. This may include a project website, targeted social media channels, press releases for wider announcements, conferences and workshops for direct interaction, and exploring other relevant channels based on the audience and project goals.

Finally, the D&C Plan recognizes the value of collaboration within the project team. By clearly defining the roles and responsibilities of each partner regarding communication activities, the plan ensures a coordinated effort that maximizes outreach potential.

6. Targeted Audiences and Key Messages

6.1 Target Audiences

AMIGDALA has initially identified several stakeholder groups who would find the project's results valuable. These groups will be targeted by the project's Dissemination, Exploitation, and Communication (DEC) activities. The project has categorized these audiences into two groups: **primary target audiences** (those who will directly use the project's solutions) and **secondary audiences** (other interested parties).

Stakeholders are individuals or groups with a vested interest in the success and outcomes of a project. They are crucial for the AMIGDALA project as their engagement, feedback, and support are essential for achieving the project's objectives. This subsection identifies and categorizes the stakeholders who will benefit from AMIGDALA. These include European, national, and regional policymakers, sectoral associations, industry stakeholders, investors, financial institutions, and the public. By adapting communication efforts to meet the needs and interests of these diverse groups, the project aims to foster broad engagement, support informed decision-making, and promote the adoption of sustainable and climate-neutral practices in line with the

European Green Deal’s objectives. More information can be found on the **D5.1 Stakeholder Engagement Plan** and on the **D5.7 Project website**.

Table 1: Stakeholder Audiences

Target Audience	Description	Impacts
Policymakers	European, national, and regional authorities responsible for designing and enforcing policies on energy, materials, industry, climate, and environment.	Science-based policymaking; assessment of policy impacts; setting and exploring policy targets; enhancing policy effectiveness.
Sectoral Associations	European and national associations representing energy-intensive industries, such as chemicals, cement, steel, aluminium, glass, and mining.	Evidence-based support for policies; identifying opportunities; preparing for future trends; enhancing credibility and influence.
Industry Stakeholders	Companies in energy-intensive industries, clean power generation, industrial manufacturing, and construction.	Access to sustainable materials and products; opportunities for decarbonization; cost savings; increased competitiveness.
Investors and Finance Sector	Investors in clean power generation and industrial manufacturing; banks and financial institutions.	Informed investment decisions; development of financing models for climate-neutral and circular solutions.
Public-Private Partnerships	Partnerships such as Processes4Planet (P4P), focusing on transforming European process industries.	Support for operational objectives, such as efficient CO ₂ valorization, circularity hubs, and market frameworks for climate-neutral solutions.
Industry Cluster Organizations	Organizations supporting member companies in implementing climate-neutral solutions.	Assistance in achieving EU climate targets; support for decarbonization initiatives; fostering collaboration and innovation.
Research and Academia	Applied research institutes, national laboratories, and universities.	Access to the latest knowledge and tools for developing new technologies; opportunities for collaboration and research advancements.
General Public	The broader community affected by industrial practices and environmental policies.	Overall reduction of emissions; improved sustainability of products and services; enhanced quality of life.

6.2 Key Messages

The success of the AMIGDALA project depends crucially on effective communication and engagement with a diverse range of stakeholders. Identifying and understanding these target audiences is crucial for tailoring D&C strategies to ensure maximum impact and uptake of project outcomes. The following table shows the target groups

identified within the AMIGDALA project and a brief description of each stakeholder group.

Work Packages	Key Messages	Target Groups
D-framework and integrated model architecture design	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Establishes the foundation for the AMIGDALA project model. Defines the framework for data integration and analysis. 	<p>Policymakers, Research and Academia</p>
Model development & PoC	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Develops core functionalities of the AMIGDALA model. Tests and validates the model's capabilities through Proof-of-Concept activities. 	<p>Policymakers, Industry Stakeholders, Research and Academia</p>
Technical completion of the integrated model and the stakeholder dashboard	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Finalizes the development of the AMIGDALA model. Creates a user-friendly dashboard for stakeholder interaction. 	<p>Policymakers, Sectoral Associations, Industry Stakeholders, Public-Private Partnerships, Industry Cluster Organizations</p>
Deploy the integrated model to evaluate pathways towards climate neutrality	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Utilizes the AMIGDALA model to simulate different scenarios for achieving climate neutrality. Provides insights into the effectiveness of various policy and industry actions. 	<p>Policymakers, Sectoral Associations, Industry Stakeholders, Public-Private Partnerships, Industry Cluster Organizations</p>
Dissemination, exploitation and communication - Reporting Period 1, 2, 3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Lays the groundwork for project communication and outreach strategies. Establishes a stakeholder management plan. Refines and implements communication strategies to reach target audiences. Develops further plans for project exploitation and intellectual property rights. Maintains ongoing communication efforts throughout the project. Identifies opportunities for project exploitation and IPR management. 	<p>All Target Groups</p>

7. Tools, Channels and Key Performance Indicators

To ensure effective communication and maximize the project's impact, AMIGDALA will utilize online tools in a strategic way to enhance outreach and impact (such as the website, newsletters or social media), channels, and KPIs. This section outlines the framework for measuring the success of the Communication and Dissemination Plan. KPIs serve as quantifiable metrics that enable the project consortium to assess progress, measure success, and identify areas for improvement in communication and dissemination activities. By setting clear and

measurable KPIs aligned with the objectives outlined in the D&C Plan, the project can track various aspects of its communication efforts, including reach, engagement, and impact. This data-driven approach not only facilitates informed decision-making but also enables timely adjustments to strategies and tactics to optimize outcomes. Additionally, well-defined KPIs provide a basis for accountability and transparency, allowing stakeholders to evaluate the project's performance against predefined benchmarks. Ultimately, the establishment of KPIs ensures that the D&C Plan remains a dynamic and responsive framework, capable of driving meaningful results and maximizing the project's overall impact and effectiveness. The goal is to deliver easily understandable information to different audiences about the project's objectives and outcomes. Leveraging the communication channels of AMIGDALA ensures that critical insights and developments are effectively disseminated to all stakeholders. This enhances engagement, supports informed decision-making, and promotes transparency, ultimately driving the successful adoption of sustainable and climate-neutral practices. The following list describes the KPIs of the project:

Table 2: KPIs as seen on the Grant Agreement

Tool/ Channel	Target Group	KPI
Scientific Publications	Academia, research teams in industries	+4 papers submitted
White Papers	Industry stakeholders	One per subsector +6 total
Scientific Workshops	Academia, research teams in industries	+3 workshops, targeting 25 attendees each. Final workshop +100 attendees
Industry Roundtables	Industries, investors	+6 roundtables
Conferences and Events Attended	All	+20 events attended
Project Website & Social Media	All	Website: 600-1,200 visits/year Social media:

		>100 followers, >2% engagement rate
Press Releases	Media	100 media outlets/articles covered
Newsletters	Academia, industry	2 per year >100 subscribers >15% opening rate
Videos	All	2 videos +300 views on YouTube
Printed Materials	All	+300 printed brochures

7.1 Scientific Publications

The inclusion of scientific publications constitutes a vital component of the AMIGDALA project. These publications serve as the primary mechanism for disseminating the project's findings, advancements, and research outcomes to the global academic and scientific community.

AMIGDALA's project partners are expected to submit at least 4 peer-reviewed scientific papers by the end of the project, ensuring Open Access. Some of the journals identified include [Open Research Europe](#), [International Journal of Production Economics](#), [Technological Forecasting and Social Change](#), or [Journal of Cleaner Production](#). After the project, effects will still be measured according to citation-based metrics such as citation counts.

The publication along the project will be encouraged, so peer reviewed feedback on the papers submitted contributes to the Open Innovation strategy of the project. The AMIGDALA project has produced one scientific paper during reporting period 1; it will be described in the actions part of this report in chapter 12.2.1.

7.2 White Papers

Once the AMIGDALA project yields specific results for sectoral transition pathways and scenarios, short white papers will be produced with the support of SIE for the graphical format. The purpose of these white papers is to provide easily understandable documents containing key

insights for industry stakeholders in the European industrial sub-sectors. One white paper will be produced for each subsector, resulting in a total of six or more.

7.3 Scientific Workshops

As described in the KPIs section of AMIGDALA, scientific workshops will be held for academic peers and industry research teams. These early presentations aim to gather feedback and share initial findings in a smaller, discussion-oriented setting (around 25 attendees). A final workshop will be organized to present the main results and outcomes of the project, targeting +100 attendees. The form will be, preliminarily, online. Cooperation with allied projects and initiatives will be sought.

Focused discussions called roundtables will be conducted with industry representatives, including investors. These discussions will help the project understand their specific needs and tailor research and development efforts accordingly. Sectoral workshops will delve deeper into specific industry requirements, and white paper presentations will directly disseminate project findings.

Project partners will actively participate in relevant conferences, workshops, and sector-related events across national, European, and international levels. This participation allows them to connect with a wider audience from academia, industry, investors, and policymakers, raising awareness about the project's goals and outcomes.

SIE will provide logistical support for all events. TNO, the project coordinator, will offer general guidance. Initially, all these events (workshops, roundtables, conferences) will be held online, with the possibility of transitioning to in-person formats depending on future developments.

7.4 Industry roundtables

In the same line of the scientific workshops, the purpose here is to receive the specific feedback of industry stakeholders, to better direct the R&D work to serve their needs and interests. Sectoral industry workshops will be organised to gather their needs and expectations, making them match the presentation of the sectoral white papers as a means of direct dissemination. Six or more will be produced.

7.5 Conferences and Events Attended

To meet target audiences, project partners will attend sector-related events, conferences, and workshops. They will also spread the word about the project's goals and outcomes. Access to target audiences at the national, European, and worldwide levels will be made possible by these events. Different events will be attended, shifting from the ones focused on academic work, to industry and investors, and policymakers.

7.6 Project Website

The AMIGDALA website serves as the primary source of information for external parties, providing regular updates on project activities and achievements for all target audiences, since its launched in month 3. It is designed to inform the community and associated industries about project developments, as well as to present the project's outcomes.

All project partners contribute to the website by providing relevant and up-to-date project information. Communication efforts and social media activities by project partners will consistently direct traffic to the AMIGDALA website. To further increase website traffic, mutual links will be created between the project partners' websites, as well as other relevant platforms and social media channels. The website includes at least one video (embedded from YouTube) to introduce the project's main objectives and ambitions. In the table below, an overview of the different pages with a short description and corresponding hyperlink is provided:

Table 3: Page content-structure of the AMIGDALA Project website.

Page	Description
Home	The home contains information about the project concept, specific objectives; and the latest project news.
About Project	The About Project tab is designed to give a more comprehensive view of the project methodology through the description of the project concept, the current challenges with the EU Green Deal, its impacts, and methodology.
About Partners	This page contains information about each of the AMIGDALA consortium partners and their main expertise.
External Advisory Board	The role of our external advisory board is to reflect with the coordinator and the project scientists on the direction and approach. Together they support us to reflect on the political, societal and

	business context of the project, techno-economic disciplines and computer modelling.
<u>Related initiatives</u>	This section is part of the clustering strategy where SIE added related initiatives such as INITIATE, GREENSTEEL, OPEN ENTRANCE. By month 18 there are more than 11 related initiatives.
<u>Documents</u>	In this section, all the public project information is being uploaded such as dissemination materials (brochure, factsheet, poster, roll up, project presentation, and logo), press releases, newsletters, scientific papers and public deliverables.
<u>Community of Practice</u>	In cooperation with Deloitte, SIE created this tab to explain and encourage the audience to subscribe to the CoP. An explanation, some practical information and a FAQ section were included.
<u>Webinars</u>	An informative section about the upcoming webinars and the recording of previous ones was included to store and share the different activities conducted within the CoP.
<u>CoP Registration</u>	A dedicated space was created to invite the different stakeholders to be part of the AMIGDALA community of practice. This page includes a form where users can sign in.
<u>News</u>	The news section is expected to be updated at least one time per month sharing information to engage with the different stakeholders. Some content examples can include partner interviews, events where the project has been showcased, milestones, etc.
<u>Contact</u>	On this page, users can send an email to the project partners. SIE will lead the email account and will share the emails with the corresponding responsible.
<u>Privacy Policy</u>	This section contains information concerning the GDPR EU regulation and how the data is protected and processed.
<u>Cookies Policy</u>	This section contains information about the cookies. The definition of the cookies, the type of cookies, and the elimination process are included.
<u>Legal Notices</u>	Finally, the legal notice refers to the general conditions that regulate the use and access to the Internet service for the project website.

The website will be maintained for the project duration and an additional two years after completion. Afterwards, SIE will delete all collected data unless legal obligations require longer storage.

Statistical data will be collected about the website visitors that subsequently will be analysed by Google Analytics software and included in the project reports. The website will be responsive to work on a variety of devices and screen sizes, such as smartphones.

SIE uses Google Analytics to analyze anonymized website traffic data. This data is included in project reports to understand user engagement. You can learn more about Google Analytics privacy practices [here](#).

More information about the project website, see deliverable D5.7 Project Website. This delivery contains the project's information (goals, work plan, partners, contact forms, etc.)

7.7 Newsletters and press releases

Digital newsletters will be prepared and distributed every 6 months. These newsletters will include project updates, announcements, interviews with partners, and other relevant information for stakeholders and subscribers. It will be distributed via MailChimp, posted on the AMIGDALA project website for easy access and on social media.

To maximize reach and engagement, project updates may also be featured in the respective digital newsletters of our partners. These partner newsletters are distributed directly to their industry-specific contact lists, further amplifying project visibility and impact.

Press releases will be published to announce noteworthy project advancements as they happen. With the support of the project partners, they will be written in English and distributed to the national media and the European press.

7.8 Project Videos

The project plans to produce at least 2 project videos will be generated. The first one, by the beginning of the project, conveying the main project objectives and impacts in a language easy to understand by non-expert audiences. The second one, by the end of the project, wrapping up the main project results and successes. SIE will develop the storyboard and after approval of all partners.

7.9 Printed Materials

SIE has created a comprehensive collection of communication materials to empower partner outreach and event participation. A [poster](#), a [factsheet](#), a [roll-up](#), a project presentation and a [brochure](#) all designed for distribution to partner networks and use at conferences, exhibitions, and other relevant events.

These materials are valuable tools for sharing project objectives, achievements, and impacts with various stakeholders, including partners, policymakers, industry professionals, and the public. By

AMIGDALA

providing complete information in different formats such as brochures, posters, and presentations, the project can improve visibility, build awareness, and foster engagement, ultimately facilitating collaboration and maximizing the project's overall impact.

Figure 1: AMIGDALA's Poster

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Figure 2: AMIGDALA Brochure

Figure 3: AMIGDALA project presentation.

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Figure 5: AMIGDALA's Roll Up

7.10 Social Media

According to the [European Research Executive Agency](#), Social media is an effective and engaging tool that allows you to instantly communicate to your audiences at a low-cost.

The project has social media presence on YouTube, X (formerly known as Twitter) and LinkedIn to ensure wider dissemination to different age groups and target audiences. These platforms will be used to not only announce project developments but, more importantly, drive traffic to the project website.

The AMIGDALA project recognizes the power of social media for reaching diverse audiences and maximizing project impact. To achieve this, the project utilizes platforms like [X] (formerly Twitter) and LinkedIn.

Beyond simply announcing project developments, AMIGDALA leverages social media to cultivate a community of interest. Since Project Month 1 (M1), consistent content has been posted, raising awareness about the project's scope and upcoming presentations. This initial phase focuses on building a strong foundation, creating a ready audience for future project results.

Social media plays a key role in driving traffic to the project website. However, effective communication goes beyond simply pushing out messages. SIE will be actively monitoring social media analytics. This allows for a deeper understanding of the audience demographics (including age groups), content performance, and user engagement with project messages (including individuals and organizations who promote the project). Based on these insights, communication efforts will be continuously optimized for maximum reach and impact.

Consortium partners are encouraged to actively engage with the project's social media channels by following, liking, commenting, and sharing posts. Additionally, partners are encouraged to share project updates on their own communication channels, such as websites and social media networks. To support this partner engagement, SIE will provide guidance and assistance on best practices for maximizing their impact.

By implementing this multifaceted social media strategy, AMIGDALA fosters a vibrant online community, optimizes communication for maximum reach, and leverages partnerships to ensure the project's information reaches a broad and diverse audience.

Figure 4: AMIGDALA LinkedIn, YouTube and X Accounts

7.11 Project Identity

The establishment of a strong project identity is essential for the effective dissemination and communication of project goals, activities, and achievements. Serving as a visual representation of the project's core values and objectives, this identity plays a key role in ensuring consistent and recognizable messaging. This section outlines the development process of the AMIGDALA project's visual identity, including the selection of a logo, the creation of brand guidelines, and the integration of required disclaimers. The communication materials underwent a visual upgrade with refreshed color schemes to enhance clarity, appeal, and overall alignment with the project's evolving branding strategy.

7.12 Project logo

AMIGDALA's visual identity started in the first month (M1) of the project. SIE led the process by presenting three logo options to all partner organizations. Partners actively participated in a democratic voting process to select the final logo. The logo features a stylized combination of the letter "G" and "D" in a modern, interconnected design. Using a gradient color scheme transitioning from green to blue to purple, it gives it a dynamic and contemporary look. Below the graphic element, the word "AMIGDALA" is written in a clean, sans-serif font, which is modern and easy to read. This ensured that the chosen design reflected

the project's shared goals and resonated with AMIGDALA's overall vision.

Figure 5: AMIGDALA Logo Options and Final Choice

7.13 Brand guidelines and templates

Recognizing the importance of a strong brand identity for successful project, AMIGDALA prioritized creating a distinct and cohesive visual language from the outset. This commitment materialized in the form of brand guidelines (see figure 2). These guidelines define a logo, a harmonious colour palette, specific typography choices, and a set of visuals. All these elements reflect the project's core principles and objectives. By ensuring a consistent presentation across all communication channels, both online and offline, this strong brand identity and emphasizes the memorability of the project.

Figure 6: AMIGDALA's Brand Guidelines

7.14 Disclaimers

According to Article 17 (Communication, dissemination, and visibility) of the Grant Agreement, the AMIGDALA project's beneficiaries have already considered the legal obligations regarding communication, dissemination, and visibility activities.

This includes providing targeted information about the project and its results to multiple audiences in a strategic, coherent, and effective manner. Before engaging in any communication or dissemination activity with significant media impact, beneficiaries informed the granting authority.

Moreover, all D&C activities related to the project, such as media relations, conferences, seminars, and information materials, have already acknowledged the support of the European Union and displayed the European flag emblem and funding statement. The European flag emblem has been displayed distinctively and separately, without modification, and no other visual identity or logo has been used to highlight EU support. When displayed alongside other logos, the European emblem has been equally prominent. The European emblem was extracted from [the official EU website](#).

Beneficiaries have utilized the European emblem for their obligations under this article without prior approval, in accordance with the grant agreement. However, it is noted that this does not grant them exclusive use rights. Additionally, they have refrained from appropriating the emblem or any similar trademark or logo. All communication and dissemination activities have used factually accurate information to maintain the quality of information provided.

To fulfil these obligations, a disclaimer has been included in all communication materials, stating, ***Funded by the European Union under the grant agreement 101138534. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Health and Digital Executive Agency (HADEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.***

In addition to the EU disclaimer, the website also features the logo of Processes4Planet, a European co-programmed public-private partnership established between [A.SPIRE](#) (the private entity) and the European Commission within the framework of Cluster 4 (Digital, Industry and Space) of the Horizon Europe funding programme. This logo will be included in specific communications. [Process4Planet](#) is a European co-programmed public-private partnership established between A.SPIRE, as the private entity, and the European Commission in the context of Cluster 4 (Digital, Industry and Space) of the Horizon Europe funding programme.

8. Community of Practice (COP)

The Community of Practice (CoP) was established in Month 1 of the AMIGDALA project, bringing together a diverse group of key

stakeholders, including industry associations, policymakers, and companies. This collaborative and voluntary group plays a central role in providing ongoing feedback and guidance throughout the project, ensuring the AMIGDALA model reflects the needs and expectations of its target users.

By actively engaging with stakeholders from the outset, the CoP helps ensure the model is not only scientifically robust but also practical and relevant for decision-makers. Their insights directly influence the design, content, and applicability of the project's final outcomes.

This section serves as a comprehensive resource on the CoP — outlining its purpose, stakeholder categories, and the value of participation. It also provides practical guidance for potential members, including how to join, stay engaged, and access the Frequently Asked Questions.

By building an inclusive and informed CoP from the start, the AMIGDALA project ensures that its outputs are grounded in real-world challenges and co-developed with those who will ultimately use them.

9. Levels of dissemination

This section explores the various levels of dissemination, noting that key target groups operate at different geographic scales. This variation influences the choice of communication tools and media, ensuring strategies are tailored to effectively reach and engage each audience segment

9.1 National Level

To ensure effective communication across Europe, the project will establish a national dissemination strategy for each partner country. This collaborative approach will involve sharing best practices for national outreach, co-organizing national events (workshops, conferences) to share project results, and contributing content to each other's D&C materials.

9.2 European Level

The European Commission will be informed about the results via the periodic reporting of the project (mid-term review, minutes of periodical meetings, updates of this document) to modify related regulations if necessary and to propose collaboration with other ongoing projects on dissemination activities.

9.3 Worldwide Level

The results will be communicated to relevant international organisations, so scientific findings can be transformed into practical information, regulations, and guidelines. Electronic resources will be disseminated via direct mail to designated organisations and stakeholders to enhance public awareness. To facilitate knowledge transfer at both research and industrial levels, technical journals, conferences, workshops at national and international levels, industry meetings, and participation in industrial forums will be used.

10. Methodology

The following internal and external D&C activities will be undertaken during the project's lifetime and afterward to ensure that the results of AMIGDALA project are efficiently and effectively communicated to the project partners, stakeholders, and broader audiences.

10.1 Internal communication

Effective internal communication is key to sharing information and ensuring that the deliverables are met. Therefore, annual face-to-face meetings and conference calls will take place to exchange project information, update progress, and share results. Consortium and technical meetings will take place at least one time a year, while Microsoft Teams and/or teleconferencing services will be used to facilitate collaboration within WPs.

Apart from specific emails, taking advantage of the at least one yearly general assembly, SIE will ask partners for their support on the upcoming dissemination and communication activities and events to update the Communication & Dissemination Plan and streamline a content curation process. This will allow the partners to take a more focused and systematic approach, strengthening actions taken to communicate and report on the project. A delegate from all consortium partners of AMIGDALA will attend this meeting.

10.2 External communication

Every effort will be made to publicize the work of the consortium via the media, publications, conference presentations, trade fairs, and workshops, as well as through the Commission and industry bodies. Results of the project will be disseminated via reports, scientific papers, and technical articles. All public communication, and in particular

scientific publications, will be made open access, to facilitate scientific exchange.

All project partners are expected to support dissemination, to ensure that stakeholders will be engaged throughout the lifetime of the project. Partners' activities may include but are not limited to engaging with relevant national and local media (print, radio, television, web-based), contributing to SIE's inputs on social media, proactively sharing information with SIE about project results, listing their communication activities in a shared file. Where possible, partners will translate press releases into their national languages and keep SIE informed about plans, by creating lists of national media channels they will try to reach.

11. Timeline

As the AMIGDALA project has different development phases, the D&C focus would be different across each of them:

11.1 Phase 1. Community building

AMIGDALA's first phase (Months 1-12) focuses on building a strong community. By setting up communication channels like a website, social media, and a mailing list, the project will reach targeted stakeholders. Engaging content will be created to explain AMIGDALA's objectives, expected results, impacts, and introduce the consortium members. Through these channels, AMIGDALA will actively engage with the community by responding to inquiries, hosting online events, and encouraging content sharing to build awareness and interest in the project.

11.2 Phase 2. R&D co-creation and diffusion

The second phase (Months 12-48) will be focused on spreading out the main scientific results of the project as they happen through different tools, enabling also the direct external feedback from peers and end users. The cooperation on technical activities with allied projects and initiatives (as P4P) will be executed in this phase.

11.3 Phase 3. Exploitation support

In parallel to the previous phase, this is focused on activities that are oriented to the uptake of the results in support of the project's exploitation strategy. This includes promotion of the software in Open

Source (OS) repositories, attending industry trade fairs, publishing papers summarizing the project's results and positive impacts.

12. Actions and Results M6-M18

12.1 Offline Actions

12.1.1 Scientific Workshops

As part of its stakeholder engagement, the AMIGDALA project hosted three events to gather input and share progress on modelling approaches for industrial decarbonization and circularity.

Workshop – 14 March 2025, Brussels

The in-person workshop brought together stakeholders from industry, policy, and research to review and provide feedback on the project's early work. The AMIGDALA team presented a draft decision-making framework, the scenario development approach, and a first look at the Proof-of-Concept model focused on plastics. Participant input will help shape the next phase of model development.

Figure 7: Decarbonization and Circularity workshop

Second Technical Webinar – 4 June 2024, online

How can models of demand, trade and industrial production provide useful information for decision-making to make industrial production in Europe climate-neutral and competitive?

During this technical webinar, we presented how AMIGDALA would contribute to resolving industry and policy maker challenges in meeting Green Deal objectives. The consortium presented AMIGDALA, including its objectives, approach, key milestones, and how you, as industrial associations, academics, or policymakers, could contribute through the new Community of Practice.

Figure 8: Second Technical Webinar

Inaugural keynote Webinar – 9 April 2024, online

AMIGDALA Project: Designing a digital twin to model the European process industry transformation to meet Green Deal Objectives.

All videos were uploaded to AMIGDALA's YouTube channel, shared on social media and posted on the website:

<https://amigdalaproject.eu/webinars/>

12.1.2 Printed Materials

At the beginning of the project, AMIGDALA produced a series of printed documents (brochure, poster, factsheet, and roll-up) to be distributed at the events attended by partners.

Figure 9: Brochures at CEPS in Brussels workshop

Figure 10: Roll-Up at Decarbonization and Circularity Workshop

Figure 11: Roll Up at General Assembly

12.1.3 Conferences and Events Attended

In these first 18 months, partners have already attended a total of [seven events](#) to disseminate the AMIGDALA project in the following events:

1. [Meet our scientists](#), June 2024. AMIGDALA was one of the 30 posters presented at the 'Meet our scientists' event, where Brightsite showcased its latest innovations, research, and projects to 100 visitors.

2. [AMIGDALA at INDTech2024 in Namur, Belgium](#) June 4, 2024. This session brought together key stakeholders from research, industry, and policymakers. The focus of INDTech2024 is on shaping the future of European industry.
3. [AMIGDALA ATTENDS THE LUX RESEARCH EVENT IN BRUSSELS](#) April 4, 2024, Lux Research organized an event aimed at presenting insights into the transformation of the steel sector and aviation, with a focus on decarbonization strategies. Among the attendees were Willem Manders and Frank Wubbolts from TNO's AMIGDALA project, who visited the event to network with companies and understand their ambitions for decarbonization.
4. [AMIGDALA Project Participates in the Launch of INCITE Event in Seville](#), June 2024. The AMIGDALA project participated in the launch of the INCITE event in Seville, Spain. INCITE is a key driver of European industry's competitiveness and green transition. Officially launched on June 21, the event brought together industry leaders, innovators, financiers, environmental NGOs, think tanks, Member States, and EU officials for an interactive exchange.
5. [The AMIGDALA project partners present at the CEFIC event](#), December 2024. Cefic, the European Chemical Industry Council, presented the outcome of their four-year project to model possible pathways for the EU chemical sector's transition towards climate-neutrality and circularity on December 9th in Brussels.
6. [TransHyDE Event – Dechema](#), March 2025. On March 6, 2025, the AMIGDALA project was presented at the TransHyDE project event in Brussels. Damien Rolland from DECHEMA introduced the project, highlighting its contributions to the broader discussion on hydrogen infrastructure and energy transformation in Europe.
7. [KEY – The Energy Transition Expo](#), June 2025. The AMIGDALA project actively contributed to the discussion on sustainability in energy technologies during a session organized by ENEA at the Hydrogen Arena, as part of [KEY – The Energy Transition Expo](#), which ran at Rimini Expo Centre.

12.2 Online Actions

12.2.1 Scientific Publications

TNO published the scientific paper ‘[The Circular Industrial Transformation System \(CITS\) model - Assessing the life cycle impacts of climate and circularity strategies](#)’, in the Journal of Cleaner Production. According to the abstract, the circular economy was introduced as a solution to mitigate increasing resource demand and to reduce environmental impacts. However, it remains a challenge to holistically assess long-term environmental impacts of circular economy strategies in complex, dynamic systems. To tackle this issue, we present the Circular Industrial Transformation System (CITS) model.

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The Circular Industrial Transformation System (CITS) model - Assessing the life cycle impacts of climate and circularity strategies

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ABSTRACT

The circular economy (CE) was introduced as a solution to mitigate increasing resource demand and to reduce environmental impacts. However, it remains a challenge to holistically assess long-term environmental impacts of CE strategies in complex, dynamic systems. To tackle this issue, we present the Circular Industrial Transformation System (CITS) model. CITS integrates dynamic stock modelling, material flow analysis and prospective life cycle assessment while being flexibly applicable to different products, materials and industry sectors across temporal and spatial scales. With that, the CITS model can assess the effect of circular strategies on long-term material flows and their respective environmental impacts, while including the effects of socio-economic developments, transformative climate policies, and a changing energy system. As a case study, the environmental impact reduction of both CE and climate change mitigation strategies was assessed for the German passenger car fleet until 2050. The results indicate that the occurring electrification of the passenger fleet is an effective strategy for reducing the global warming impacts of the automotive sector in the long-term, albeit aligned with the renewable energy transformation. CE strategies are most effective in reducing CO₂-eq. emissions in the short term. Particularly, CE strategies affecting the vehicle stock promise substantial reductions in CO₂-eq. emissions and primary material demand, while improved collection, sorting, and recycling have a limited impact. The results show that the CITS model can guide policies in effectively reducing environmental impacts in complex, dynamic systems by identifying system bottlenecks, trade-offs or synergies in industrial transitions.

List of abbreviations

Abbreviation	Description	Source
LCA	Life cycle assessment	
P-LCA	Prospective life cycle assessment	
MFA	Material flow analysis	
DSM	Dynamic stock modelling	
IAM	Integrated assessment model	
CITS	Circular Industrial Transformation System	

(continued)

Abbreviation	Description	Source
GHG	Greenhouse gas	
HDPE	High density polyethylene	
LDPE	Low density polyethylene	
PP	Polypropylene	
PET	Polyethylene terephthalate	
PS	Polystyrene	
PVC	Polyvinyl chloride	
BCP	Representative Concentration Pathways	(Fricko et al., 2017; Rada et al., 2022; Saechi et al., 2022)

Figure 12: First Scientific Publication

12.2.2 Project Website

The AMIGDALA project launched its website in Month 3, providing a central hub for all project information. Since then, the website has grown from M6 to M18 to include all key activities, updates, articles, and documents created within the AMIGDALA project. In the [News section](#), 30 posts were published in the past months:

1. [AMIGDALA PLOTTING PATHWAYS TOWARDS SUSTAINABLE INDUSTRIAL PRODUCTION](#)
2. [THE AMIGDALA PROJECT HOSTS ITS KICK-OFF MEETING IN FRANKFURT](#)
3. [WHAT IS AMIGDALA? PAVING THE WAY FOR EUROPE'S GREEN FUTURE BY ANALYSING COMPLEX INDUSTRY TRANSFORMATION TOWARDS CLIMATE NEUTRALITY](#)
4. [AMIGDALA HOLDS A MODEL WORKSHOP IN UTRECHT](#)
5. [AMIGDALA HOLDS ITS INAUGURAL KEYNOTE](#)
6. [THE AMIGDALA PROJECT, MEMBER OF THE PROCESS4PLANET PARTNERSHIP](#)
7. [AMIGDALA ATTENDS THE LUX RESEARCH EVENT IN BRUSSELS](#)
8. [AMIGDALA at INDTech2024 in Namur, Belgium](#)
9. [AMIGDALA at 'Meet our scientists' event](#)
10. [AMIGDALA newsletter](#)
11. [AMIGDALA Project Participates in the Launch of INCITE Event in Seville](#)
12. [AMIGDALA's Project General Assembly](#)
13. [BFI's contributions as a partner in the AMIGDALA project](#)
14. [DECHEMA's Role in the AMIGDALA Project: Leading Data Expertise and Management for Comprehensive Modeling Support](#)
15. [Closing knowledge gaps and reducing uncertainties to support the EU's green industrial transition](#)
16. [Successful workshop at CEPS in Brussels](#)
17. [GreenDecision's Role in the AMIGDALA Project](#)
18. [KU Leuven's Agent-Based Modeling in the AMIGDALA Project](#)
19. [Interview with Celine Fellay: Sitech's Role in the AMIGDALA Project](#)
20. [The AMIGDALA project partners present at the CEFIC event](#)
21. [ENEA's Role in the AMIGDALA Project](#)

22. [AMIGDALA Project's General Assembly in Münster, Germany](#)
23. [Upcoming AMIGDALA Project: Comprehensive modelling of transformative pathways for European industrial decarbonization and circularity – Workshop to design key dimensions](#)
24. [The AMIGDALA Project Presented at TransHyDE Event](#)
25. [AMIGDALA Project Participation in ENEA's Sustainability Session at Hydrogen Arena](#)
26. [Comprehensive modelling of transformative pathways for European industrial decarbonization and circularity – Workshop Highlights](#)
27. [From Data to Decisions: An Interview with Olivier Jan, Partner at Deloitte Sustainability France](#)
28. [Integrating GLOBIOM into AMIGDALA: Advancing Land-Use Modeling with IIASA](#)
29. [AMIGDALA General Assembly in Leuven](#)
30. [Policy Lab partners with the AMIGDALA project to support Europe's transition to sustainable and resilient industries](#)

The About section now includes two updates: a new External Advisory Board section and additional items under Related Initiatives. Further details about clustering can be found in 12.2.5 Clustering.

External Advisory Board: the role of AMIGDALA's external advisory board is to reflect with the coordinator and the project scientists on the direction and approach. Together they support us to reflect on the

political, societal and business context of the project, techno-economic disciplines, and computer modelling.

EXTERNAL ADVISORY BOARD

The External Advisory Board

The role of our external advisory board is to reflect with the coordinator and the project scientists on the direction and approach. Together they support us to reflect on the political, societal and business context of the project, techno-economic disciplines and computer modelling.

1. The ambitions for European society and for Europe's leadership on global transformation
2. The business opportunity for industry to realize society's ambitions through investments and divestments
3. Process systems engineering
4. Unlocking of industry feedstock from circular and renewable origin
5. The generation and distribution of clean or renewable energy
6. The analysis of transformation pathways by integrated computer models

AMIGDALA and its sister project [TRANSIENCE](#) have a seat in each others' advisory boards to seek alignment and exploit synergies.

Pierre Joris

Prof. André Bardow

Louis Meuleman

Konstantinos Koasidis

Sebastian Engell

Rahmat Poudineh

Figure 13: External Advisory Board

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European Union

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Figure 14: Related Initiatives

The AMIGDALA website attracted a total of **6.972 views**, who collectively browsed the site through **3.578 sessions** (last update May 28, 2025). This translates to an average of **1.8 sessions per user**. In terms of geographic distribution, users from the United States topped the list at 505, followed by those from the Netherlands (348), Spain (187), Belgium (146), and Germany (138). The **engagement rate** was healthy, reaching **49.47%** of the audience, this suggests that users are finding the website content interesting and spending time interacting with it.

Figure 15: Audience Overview

Figure 16: Language Breakdown

Figure 17: AMIGDALA Homepage

12.2.3 Newsletter and Press Releases

Every six months, electronic newsletters containing project updates, news, interviews, and other AMIGDALA-related information will be published. These newsletters are sent to stakeholders and partner networks as well as uploaded on the [project website](#).

- [First Newsletter](#). June 17, 2024

On June 2024, the AMIGDALA project published its [first newsletter](#) with the key objectives of the project, we presented the concept of our Community of Practice, inviting members to engage and collaborate. The newsletter also highlighted upcoming and past webinars, as well as conferences and events of interest to our network. Finally, we shared links to our partners' social media channels to help you stay connected and informed.

Since multiple stakeholders have contributed, the stakeholder list includes more than 96 contacts.

Figure 18: First Newsletter

- [Second Newsletter](#). December 10, 2025

The second newsletter focused on key developments in the project, including the General Assembly held in Amsterdam, which served as a platform for partners to review progress and coordinate upcoming activities. It also highlighted a successful workshop organised at CEPS in Brussels, fostering meaningful exchange among stakeholders. The edition featured interviews with three project partners, providing insights into their contributions and perspectives. Additionally, it included links to newly published public deliverables and partner social media accounts to facilitate broader dissemination and engagement.

PLOTTING PATHWAYS TOWARDS SUSTAINABLE INDUSTRIAL PRODUCTION

Explore our latest updates and insights to stay informed, inspired, and prepared to make a difference.

GENERAL ASSEMBLY

On June 19-20, 2024, AMIGDALA project partners gathered at TNO's facilities in Amsterdam for the project's first General Assembly. Over these two days, partners presented the initial results of their work from the past six months, setting the stage for insightful discussions and collaborative progress. Hosted by TNO, the meeting focused on reviewing technical advancements, defining next steps, and presenting recent results from various work packages.

[READ MORE](#)

Figure 19: Second Newsletter

- [Third Newsletter](#). June 19, 2025

The [third newsletter](#) presented a range of project updates and dissemination activities. It featured new interviews with project partners, offering further insight into their roles and ongoing work. Coverage included the recent General Assembly held in Leuven. It also introduced the project's first video and provided an update on the activities of the External Advisory Board. Past events were highlighted, along with a reminder to engage with the Community of Practice. As in previous editions, links to partner social media channels were included to support continued outreach and visibility.

NEWSLETTER 3 | JUNE 2020

AMIGDALA

PLOTTING PATHWAYS TOWARDS SUSTAINABLE INDUSTRIAL PRODUCTION

Explore our latest updates and insights to stay informed, inspired, and prepared to make a difference.

INTRODUCING THE FIRST PROJECT VIDEO

GENERAL ASSEMBLY (LEUVEN)

The AMIGDALA Project General assembly took place on May 27-28 in Leuven, hosted by our partner VITO. It was a productive meeting that brought together project partners to share progress and prepare for the upcoming first review meeting in July. A highlight of the meeting was the official welcome of our new partner, Policy Lab, who will enhance the project's capacity to deliver advanced scenario modeling and market forecasts to guide the transformation of energy-intensive industries across Europe.

Figure 20: Third Newsletter

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The first **press release** was launched with information about the kickoff meeting. Sustainable Innovations Europe (SIE) - the project's dissemination partner - and the consortium partners forwarded the first [press release](#) to approximately 500 trade and local media outlets. It was published in [WIT NEWS](#) website.

The [second press release](#), titled 'Shaping Europe's Green Industrial Future: AMIGDALA Workshop on Decarbonization & Circularity', announced the workshop hosted by the AMIGDALA project. Held last March 14, 2025, at Silversquare Europe in Brussels, the event aimed to support the modelling of transformative pathways for industrial decarbonization and circularity.

The [third press release](#), titled 'Policy Lab Joins AMIGDALA Project to Strengthen Strategic Insights into European Industry Transformation', announced the addition of a new project partner. Policy Lab. It was sent on June 17, 2025. It was featured in [Open PR](#).

The following images are part of the clipping of the press releases:

Figure 21: Clipping for the first press release, published on WIT NEWS

Worldwide Public Relations

PR-Wiki | Inprint

Categories | Submit Press Release | 0

Press release

Policy Lab Joins AMIGDALA Project to Strengthen Strategic Insights into European Industry Transformation

06-18-2025 09:04 AM CET | [Energy & Environment](#)
 Press release from: [Sustainable Innovations \(SIE\)](#)

 [The AMIGDALA Project](#)

The AMIGDALA Project team, comprising economists and data scientists, brings extensive experience in export promotion, economic resilience, and the strategic positioning of companies within global supply chains.

Policy Lab, a private research centre specializing in big data science solutions for global trade strategies and economic development policies, has officially joined the Horizon Europe-funded AMIGDALA project. The team, comprising economists and data scientists, brings extensive experience in export promotion, economic resilience, and the strategic positioning of companies within global supply chains.

By joining AMIGDALA, Policy Lab strengthens the project's capacity to provide strategic insights into the transformation of energy-intensive industries in Europe, with a focus on aligning decarbonization with long-term competitiveness.

Launched in January 2024, AMIGDALA aims to develop an integrated model suite to explore viable pathways for energy-intensive industries to contribute to the EU's climate neutrality goals. This includes modelling how industry can become climate neutral across energy use, emissions, and feedstock transitions, while supporting effective policymaking at both EU and national levels. Policy Lab will contribute to advanced scenario modelling and market foresight tools that project the uptake of transformative solutions under selected framework conditions.

These insights are key to helping industry leaders and policymakers anticipate system-wide shifts and make informed decisions about industrial innovation, infrastructure investment, and trade dynamics.

The consortium is coordinated by TNO and includes leading partners such as BFI, Catholic University of Leuven, DECHEMA, Deloitte, ENEA, European Research Services, GreenDecision, IIASA, SITECH, Sustainable Innovations, and VITO. The addition of Policy Lab enriches the project with strategic intelligence to navigate the complexities of industrial transformation in a globalized economy.

HNK building
 Radanweg 60
 1043 NT Amsterdam
 The Netherlands

About AMIGDALA
 AMIGDALA aims to achieve impact by providing European legislators and industries insights into the interaction between regulatory action and the global industrial investment response. This innovative approach thus drives sustainability while it considers strategic positioning, global competitiveness and resilience. Led by the research centre TNO (The Netherlands), the AMIGDALA project is formed by BFI, the Catholic University of Leuven, DECHEMA, Deloitte, ENEA, European Research Services, GreenDecision, IIASA, SITECH, Sustainable Innovations, and VITO. The AMIGDALA project has been programmed under the Process4Planet partnership and is supported by the European Union under the Grant Agreement number 101138534. amigdalaproject.eu

Figure 22: Clipping regarding the third press release published on Open PR

Funded by the European Union under the grant agreement 101138534. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Health and Digital Executive Agency (HADEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

12.2.4 Project Videos

As mentioned in the Grant Agreement, at least two project videos will be generated. The first project video was released in January 2025 and uploaded to the official YouTube channel, conveying the main project objectives and impacts in a language easy to understand by non-expert audiences.

Figure 23: Project Video

12.2.5 Clustering

As mentioned in chapter 7, the Related Initiatives section was included on the project's website with the 16 related initiatives: The INITIATE project, [Green Steel for Europe](#), [TRANSCIENCE](#), [openENTRANCE](#) and [Hubs4Circularity](#), amongst others. The AMIGDALA project has become a part of the [Process4Planet partnership](#), a European initiative aimed at transforming the process industries to achieve circularity and climate neutrality across the European Union by 2050, while boosting their global competitiveness.

The AMIGDALA project has initiated collaboration with the Processes4Planet Partnership and is included in its Cooperation Plan (D5.4).

AMIGDALA's webinars have been shared on the P4Planet website, and the SIE team contacted the partnership to help promote them within its network. These actions support the project's alignment with P4Planet's objective to transition European process industries toward circularity and climate neutrality by 2050. AMIGDALA also took part in the [INDTech 2024 Conference](#) (as described in chapter 12.1.3) through an invitation from A.SPIRE. A free booth was provided to present the project's work and engage with other P4Planet initiatives. This participation helped increase visibility within the community and contributed to the project's dissemination and stakeholder outreach.

Figure 24: AMIGDALA Related Initiatives

On 22 October 2024, the AMIGDALA project, in collaboration with the [TRANSCIENCE project](#), hosted a joint workshop to tackle the complex challenges posed by the dual transition towards a circular and carbon-neutral economy. These challenges are particularly acute for energy-intensive sectors, where uncertainty can significantly hinder investment decisions. To support industry and policymakers in

navigating these uncertainties, the EU-funded Horizon Europe projects AMIGDALA and TRANSCIENCE are developing advanced modelling capacities. This workshop brought together stakeholders from policy, industry, academia, and civil society to identify key transition barriers, explore feasible solutions, and promote the use of improved modelling tools in guiding the EU's industrial transformation. By focusing on priority areas and real-world needs, the two projects aim to deliver scientific support that is both relevant and actionable. The event also addressed the critical need for clear transition roadmaps and enabling environments, ensuring that modelling efforts contribute effectively to Europe's sustainability goals.

Figure 25: TRANSCIENCE and AMIDALA promotional image for the workshop

Figure 26: TRANSCIENCE Instagram promotion

During the M6–M18 period, the AMIGDALA project has made substantial progress in clustering efforts that align closely with its strategic goals. By actively engaging with the Processes4Planet Partnership, participating in key events such as INDTech 2024, and co-organising a joint workshop with the TRANSCIENCE project, AMIGDALA has strengthened its role within the European research and innovation landscape. These activities have supported greater visibility, facilitated knowledge exchange, and contributed to the development of actionable modelling tools for a circular and climate-neutral industry.

12.2.6 Community of practice

During the M6–M18 reporting period, the Community of Practice (CoP) continued to serve as an important element of the AMIGDALA project's stakeholder engagement activities. Established during the release of the website, the CoP has grown, bringing together stakeholders from industry, policymaking, academia, and civil society. Throughout this period, members were engaged through targeted communications, invitations to webinars, and opportunities to provide feedback on project developments. The dedicated CoP section on the AMIGDALA website was regularly updated as a live document, offering current information on the CoP's goals, benefits, FAQs, and registration process. These updates helped keep the CoP accessible, informative, and

responsive to ongoing project needs. SIE published monthly reminders on LinkedIn and X to subscribe to the Community of Practice. Each reminder included a direct link, effectively highlighting the CoP's value and encouraging immediate subscriptions.

Figure 27: Community of Practice web section

Figure 28: Monthly CoP updates on LinkedIn

12.2.7 Impact on media outlets and other relevant websites

WIT NEWS

<https://witnews.eu/policy-lab-joins-amigdala-project-to-strengthen-strategic-insights-into-european-industry-transformation/>

Open PR

<https://www.openpr.com/news/4070567/policy-lab-joins-amigdala-project-to-strengthen-strategic>

WIT NEWS

<https://witnews.eu/amigdala-a-project-to-boost-the-industrial-transformation/>

Brightsite

<https://brightsitecenter.com/integrating-models-for-a-sustainable-industrial-future-a-conversation-with-celine-fellay-on-the-amigdala-project/>

A.SPIRE

<https://www.aspire2050.eu/news/new/process-industries-context-european-green-deal>

A.SPIRE

<https://www.aspire2050.eu/news/new/amigdala-plotting-pathways-towards-sustainable-industrial-production>

Sustainable Innovations

<https://sustainableinnovations.eu/es/np-amigdala-2024-proyecto-pacto-verde/>

13. Dissemination Tables

The Dissemination tables hosted in the AMIGDALA SharePoint, detail specific dissemination actions, timelines, responsible partners, and communication methods, ensuring a coordinated and effective approach to reaching stakeholders.

Partner	Dissemination activity name	What? Type of dissemination	Who? Target audience Reached	Why? Description of the objective(s) with reference to a specific project output (max 200 characters)	Status of the dissemination activity	Relevant link	Date
VITO	Presentation introducing AMIGDALA	Meetings	Other	Present AMIGDALA to Joint Research Centre Unit C7 Energy Transition Insights for Policy	Delivered	https://amigdalaproject.eu/2	MARCH 2024
TNO	LUX RESEARCH: re-tooling of industry for the GreenDeal	Conferences	EU Institutions	Meet potential stakeholders within the EU Green Deal framework	Delivered		apr-24
DEL		Conferences	EU Institutions	Meet potential stakeholders within the EU Green Deal framework	Delivered		apr-24
VITO	IndTech 2024	Conferences	Industry, business partners	Transformation of European Energy Intensive Industries on the way	Delivered	https://amigdalaproject.eu/2	JUNE 2024
TNO	INCITE Event 2024	Conferences	Industry, business partners	European Innovation Centre for Industrial Transformation and Emissions (INCITE) launch event	Delivered		JUNE 2024
SIT	Meet our scientists Brightsite	Conferences	Industry, business partners	AMIGDALA was one of the 30 posters presented at the 'Meet our scientists' event, where Brightsite showcased its latest innovations, research, and projects	Delivered	https://amigdalaproject.eu/2	JUNE 2024
TNO	Closing knowledge gaps and reducing uncertainties to support th	Conferences	Industry, business partners	Workshop at CEPS in Brussels in support of the transition to a circular and carbon-neutral economy	Delivered	https://amigdalaproject.eu/2	OCTOBER 2024
TNO	Presentation of the IC2050 model of CEFIC	Conferences	Industry, business partners		Delivered	https://amigdalaproject.eu/2	nov-24
TNO	Workshop	Other	Industry, business partners	Comprehensive modelling of transformative pathways for	Delivered	https://amigdalaproject.eu/2	February 2025

				European industrial decarbonization and circularity – Workshop to design key dimensions			
DEC	TransHyDE Event	Clustering activities	Research communities	On March 6, 2025, the AMIGDALA project was presented at the TransHyDE project event in Brussels. Damien Rolland from DECHEMA introduced the project, highlighting its contributions to the broader discussion on hydrogen infrastructure and energy transformation in Europe.	Delivered	https://amigdalaproject.eu/2	March 2025
ENEA	ENEA's Sustainability Session at Hydrogen Arena	Conferences	Industry, business partners	KEY – The Energy Transition Expo, which ran at Rimini Expo Centre from March 5-7, 2025. This event, chaired by Alessandro Agostini and Giuseppe Pellegrini Masini, explored the environmental, economic, and social impacts of renewable fuels of non-biological origin in the transition to a zero-emission energy system.	Delivered	https://amigdalaproject.eu/2	March 2025

Figure 29: Dissemination Table

Partner	DATE (MONTH/YEAR)	Communication Activity Name	Description	Who? Target audience	How? Communication channel	PLACE	Outcome	Status	Relevant link
SIE	FEBRUARY 2024	PRESS RELEASE	SIE PARTICIPATES IN THE AMIGDALA PROJECT	Civil_society	Press_Release	WEBSITE	500	Delivered	https://sustainableinnovations.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/02/PR-AMIGDALA-2024.pdf
SIE	FEBRUARY 2024	SOCIAL MEDIA POST	KOM	Civil_society	Social_Media	LINKEDIN	8200	Delivered	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7156581264819421184
SIE	FEBRUARY 2024	SOCIAL MEDIA POST	KOM	Civil_society	Social_Media	TWITTER	1200	Delivered	https://twitter.com/SustainableInnE/status/1750816316502532437
SIE	FEBRUARY 2024	SOCIAL MEDIA POST	KOM	Civil_society	Social_Media	INSTAGRAM	540	Delivered	https://www.instagram.com/p/C2xt1xswsk/?img_index=1
SIE	FEBRUARY 2024	SOCIAL MEDIA POST	PRESS RELEASE ANNOUNCEMENT	Civil_society	Social_Media	LINKEDIN	8200	Delivered	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7159153180902141952
SIE	FEBRUARY 2024	SOCIAL MEDIA POST	PRESS RELEASE ANNOUNCEMENT	Civil_society	Social_Media	TWITTER	1200	Delivered	https://twitter.com/SustainableInnE/status/1753387839889293427
SIE	FEBRUARY 2024	SOCIAL MEDIA POST	PRESS RELEASE ANNOUNCEMENT	Civil_society	Social_Media	INSTAGRAM	540	Delivered	https://www.instagram.com/p/C22iD6nNmUZ/
SIE	FEBRUARY 2024	WEBSITE POST	PRESS RELEASE ANNOUNCEMENT	Civil_society	Website	WEBSITE	1000	Delivered	https://sustainableinnovations.eu/pr-amigdala-2024-green-deal-project/
DEC	JANUARY 2024	SOCIAL MEDIA POST	KOM	Civil_society	Social_Media	X (Twitter)	185	Delivered	https://x.com/AmigdalaProject/status/1750494455725957282?e=20
DEC	FEBRUARY 2024	SOCIAL MEDIA POST	KOM	Civil_society	Social_Media	LinkedIn	1250	Delivered	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/dechema_ziel-des-projekts-amigdala-ist-die-erforschung-activity7162807892973191168-4M1B?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop
DEC	FEBRUARY 2024	NEWSLETTER	KOM	Civil_society	Newsletter	Newsletter	19300 recipients (opening rate 28%)	Delivered	
DEC	FEBRUARY 2024	PRESS RELEASE	KOM	Civil_society	Press_Release	WEBSITE	686 (website opened)	Delivered	
A.SPIRE	FEBRUARY 2024	AMIGDALA	AMIGDALA. Plotting pathways towards sustainable industrial production	Civil_society	Website	WEBSITE	1000	Delivered	https://www.aspire2050.eu/news/new/amigdala-plotting-pathways-towards-sustainable-industrial-production
ALL	MARCH 2024	2nd Webinar	AMIGDALA 2ND WEBINAR	Civil_society	Website	WEBSITE	1000	Delivered	https://www.aspire2050.eu/news/new/process-industries-context-european-green-deal
VITO	MARCH 2024	Presentation introducing AMIGDALA	Present AMIGDALA to Joint Research Centre Unit C7 Energy Transition Insights for Policy	EU_Institutions	Other	Virtual Presentation	25 attendees	Delivered	
BFI	FEBRUARY 2024	REPOST ON SOCIAL MEDIA	KOM	Civil_society	Social_Media	KOM	521	Delivered	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:ugcPost:71158106342442897408/?actorCompanyId=101246398
ENEA	MARCH 2024	REPOST ON SOCIAL MEDIA	AMIGDALA COP WORKSHOP	Civil_society	Social_Media	LINKEDIN	132000	Delivered	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:share:7178359261440139265/?actorCompanyId=101246398
ENEA	MARCH 2024	REPOST ON SOCIAL MEDIA	AMIGDALA 1ST PRESS RELEASE	Civil_society	Social_Media	LINKEDIN	132000	Delivered	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:ugcPost:7117982014917140481/?actorCompanyId=101246398
DEL	apr-24	REPOST ON SOCIAL MEDIA	AMIGDALA 2ND WEBINAR	Civil_society	Social_Media	LINKEDIN	521	Delivered	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:share:718677697466352545/?actorCompanyId=101246398
BFI	MAY 2024	REPOST ON SOCIAL MEDIA	AMIGDALA 2ND WEBINAR	Civil_society	Social_Media	LINKEDIN	596	Delivered	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7190717604318130176/?actorCompanyId=101246398

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ENE	MAY 2024	SOCIAL MEDIA POST	AMIGDALA 2ND WEBINAR	Civil_society	Social_Media	LINKEDIN	599	Delivered	https://www.linkedin.com/in/alessandro-agostini-a924485/
ENE	MAY 2024	REPOST ON SOCIAL MEDIA	AMIGDALA 2ND WEBINAR	Civil_society	Social_Media	LINKEDIN	596	Delivered	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:share:7191752097791406080/?actorCompanyId=101246398
SIT	MAY 2024	SOCIAL MEDIA POST	Interview Céline Fellay	Civil_society	Social_Media	LINKEDIN	2000	Delivered	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7191685919064653825/?actorCompanyId=101246398
DEC	MAY 2024	SOCIAL MEDIA POST	AMIGDALA 2ND WEBINAR	Civil_society	Social_Media	LINKEDIN	286	Delivered	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:share:7197118991985713152/?actorCompanyId=101246398
ERS	MAY 2024	SOCIAL MEDIA POST	AMIGDALA 2ND WEBINAR	Civil_society	Social_Media	LINKEDIN	286	Delivered	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:share:7197118991985713152/?actorCompanyId=101246398
SIE	JUNE 2024	SOCIAL MEDIA POST	AMIGDALA	Civil_society	Social_Media	LINKEDIN	286	Delivered	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7201153844418953216/?actorCompanyId=101246398
TNO	JUNE 2024	SOCIAL MEDIA POST	AMIGDALA 2ND WEBINAR	Civil_society	Social_Media	LINKEDIN	8700	Delivered	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:share:7199736688288354304/?actorCompanyId=101246398
TNO	JUNE 2024	SOCIAL MEDIA POST	AMIGDALA 2ND WEBINAR	Civil_society	Social_Media	LINKEDIN	600	Delivered	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:share:7199667003060568064/?actorCompanyId=101246398
VITO	JUNE 2024	SOCIAL MEDIA POST	AMIGDALA 2ND WEBINAR	Civil_society	Social_Media	LINKEDIN	500	Delivered	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:share:7197152218129514496/?actorCompanyId=101246398
VITO	JUNE 2024	SOCIAL MEDIA POST	INDtech	Civil_society	Social_Media	LINKEDIN	300	Delivered	https://amigdalaproject.eu/2024/06/05/amigdala-at-indtech2024-in-namur-belgium/
ALL	JUNE 2024	NEWSLETTER	AMIGDALA's First Newsletter	Civil_society	Newsletter	Newsletter	96	Delivered	https://mailchi.mp/6bd3a0bf153/amigdala-newsletter-1-june-2024
SIE	JULY 2024	SOCIAL MEDIA POST	Corporate Post	Civil_society	Newsletter	Newsletter	8640	Delivered	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7216331752087154689/
SIE	JULY 2024	SOCIAL MEDIA POST	AMIGDALA GA	Civil_society	Newsletter	Newsletter	8640	Delivered	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7209551705837871105/?actorCompanyId=101246398
GD	March 2025	SOCIAL MEDIA POST	Report LinkedIn	Civil_society	Social_Media	LINKEDIN	500	Delivered	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:share:7303205400193990656/?actorCompanyId=101246398
GD	March 2025	SOCIAL MEDIA POST	KeyEnergy Rimini	Civil_society	Social_Media	LINKEDIN	500	Delivered	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7303210307496079360/?actorCompanyId=101246398
GD	March 2025	SOCIAL MEDIA POST	GreenDecision at the AMIGDALA Workshop in Brussels!	Civil_society	Social_Media	LINKEDIN	500	Delivered	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7308096984664453120/?actorCompanyId=101246398
ERS	MAY 2025	SOCIAL MEDIA POST	Repost Linkedl	Civil_society	Social_Media	LINKEDIN	500	Delivered	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:share:7333138621375410176/?actorCompanyId=101246398
VITO	MAY 2025	SOCIAL MEDIA POST	Repost Linkedl	Civil_society	Social_Media	LINKEDIN	500	Delivered	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7333241246154387456/?actorCompanyId=101246398
POL LAB	MAY 2025	SOCIAL MEDIA POST	Hop On	Civil_society	Social_Media	LINKEDIN	202	Delivered	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7325060952171728896/?actorCompanyId=101246398

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SIE	MAY 2025	SOCIAL MEDIA POST	GA in Leuven	Civil_society	Social_Media	LINKEDIN	9000	Delivered	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7333427882116927489/?actorCompanyId=101246398
GD	MAY 2025	SOCIAL MEDIA POST	GA in Leuven	Civil_society	Social_Media	LINKEDIN	569	Delivered	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7333860889017671681/?actorCompanyId=101246398
BFI	JUNE 2025	SOCIAL MEDIA POST	GA in Leuven	Civil_society	Social_Media	LINKEDIN	956	Delivered	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7335649286086455296/?actorCompanyId=101246398

Figure 30: Communication activities